

Between Paid Work and Time Giving: The Motivations of Volunteer Involvement in Côte d'Ivoire.

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Abstract

More and more people are committing themselves to work for free in non-profit organizations. Knowing what motivates them is a major issue if we want to increase their numbers in view of the importance of their work. At a time when all eyes are on the fight against unemployment, especially youth unemployment, volunteering is a possible solution. Young people get their first work experience through volunteering, which improves their employability. The aim of this study is to understand the factors that explain voluntary involvement. Based on a simple Tobit model with double censorship and using data from the 2014 employment survey, the study shows that the prevailing motivation for volunteering stems from the relationship with parents from an early age. It is guided by socio-demographic characteristics, mainly religion, and reinforced by the individual's employment structure, whether private or associative.

Keywords : volunteer motivation, volunteer involvement, volunteer work, paid work.

Résumé

De plus en plus de personnes s'engagent à travailler gratuitement dans les organismes à but non lucratif. La connaissance de ce qui les motive est un enjeu majeur si l'on veut accroître leur nombre à la vue de l'importance de leur action. Au moment où tous les regards sont tournés vers la lutte contre le chômage, celui des jeunes en particulier, le bénévolat se présente comme une piste de solution. Les jeunes font une première expérience professionnelle à travers le bénévolat ce qui améliore leur employabilité. L'objectif de cette étude est de comprendre les facteurs explicatifs de l'engagement bénévole. A partir d'un modèle Tobit simple à double censure alimenté par les données de l'enquête emploi de 2014, l'étude montre que la motivation qui prévaut à l'engagement bénévole naît de la relation avec les parents depuis le bas âge. Elle est guidée par les caractéristiques sociodémographiques, principalement la religion et renforcée par la structure employeuse de l'individu, qu'elle soit privée ou associative.

Mots clés : motivation bénévole, engagement bénévole, travail bénévole, travail salarié.

1. Introduction

A new dynamism is noted in the commitment of volunteers in Côte d'Ivoire from 2011. The number of people engaged in volunteer activities has increased considerably. They are very present in the work of mutual aid, charity and act with great empathy. Their donation of time for unpaid work contributes to the smooth running of the community. They are also present in private or public structures and work a few hours a week with little or no financial compensation. Since then, the number of associations and organizations using volunteer labour has become more important. They can be found in almost all sectors of activity. Indeed, volunteers make up the bulk of the labour required to run most associations (Prouteau and Wolf, 2004a).

For a long time, this sector of activity was sidelined because it did not generate much economic interest. Volunteering is the giving of time to carry out an unpaid activity in a non-profit institution (Bjarne Ibsen, 1992). It involves activities that produce goods and services that contain value for those who benefit from them (Prouteau and Wolf, 2004b). It is an activity that, when measured, should contribute to the production of goods and services that are part of the general output of the economy as defined in the System of National Accounts (SNA). If it is carried out through an organization, it is referred to as formal volunteering. In most cases this structure is an association, a cooperative, a mutual society, an NGO or a foundation. Although the host organization may be a public administration (Halba and Le net, 1997).

A study of the Ivorian labour market reveals disparities and points that need to be closely assessed. In 2013, 52.7% of the working-age population is actually in employment, and 0.6% of this population does formal volunteer work through NGOs and associations (AGEPE/INS, 2013). In 2015, 93.11% of the working-age population is actually working. This time, volunteering is not specified, however, 8.3% reported doing family assistance and 1.1% could not be classified (INS / ENV, 2015). It is therefore certain that volunteers are contained in the latter two groups. The question this research answers is: What motivates the involvement of volunteers?

2. Objectives

The main objective of this study is to analyse the factors that explain voluntary involvement in Côte d'Ivoire. In a clear and specific way, it is about :

- To show the influence of socio-demographic characteristics in the choice to do volunteer work;
- Analyze the impact of the socio-professional environment on volunteer involvement ;
- Determine the influence of parents on the choice to engage in volunteer work.

Knowledge of what motivates volunteer involvement is necessary in the struggle for socialization and the development of altruism. It would encourage the development of adequate employment policies. Certainly,

the structures employing volunteer labour would find in this work an orientation in the search for and retention of their volunteers.

In order to achieve these different objectives, the methodology used consists of analysing, first of all, the results of a survey we carried out on the motivations of volunteers. This survey was carried out between October and November 2016 using a set of 30 questions addressed to different volunteer populations.

Secondly, emphasis will be placed on data from employment policy management agency (AGEPE) 2013 employment survey, whose database is essential for taking volunteers into account at the national level. In order to link the socio-professional situation of the population with volunteer commitment, the statistics provided by the NSI's (National statistic institute) report on the standard of living of households in 2015 have been consulted.

3. Literature review

3.1. Brief review of the social solidarity-based economy

The social and solidarity economy (SSE) is a group of mutuals, cooperatives, foundations and associations working for the economic and social well-being of populations. The American continent dominated by the two largest countries, Canada and the United States of America (USA), is very present in the practice of voluntary activities. The USA is a traditionally voluntary country. Since the colonial period, the various states have been made up of inhabitants who survived only by the practice of solidarity and mutual aid in exploitative work. The occupants, new and old, all had the same objective : to survive. In this case, cooperation was obvious, and even today working through an SSE enterprise is more than a source of pride for an American. In Canada, in 2012, more than 47% of the population volunteered. In 2006, there were 12.5 million people involved in volunteer activities through 165,000 organizations and contributed 2.1 billion hours (Imagine Canada, 2012; Lasby & Barr, 2012). All companies have a high degree of corporate social responsibility, so all new recruits are required to have a volunteer background and commit to volunteering from time to time at the initiative of the employer. In France, associations that operate through volunteering constitute the largest part of the Social and Solidarity Economy (SSE). The majority of workers in this sector are salaried employees. In 2013, it accounted for 10.5% of employment, 13.9% of private employment, 15% of women's employment, more than 25% of employees have been in the SSE since 2000. This area offers 600,000 positions to be filled by the year 2020 due to retirements according to the CNCRES (Insee Clap 2013 figures).

In West Africa, working through SSE structures is a daily practice embedded in cultures. In the fields, farming practices are painful, the only way to ensure higher yields is to join forces, so social entrepreneurship is the intrinsic link between agricultural producers and consumers. Groups and associations that do not say their names exist as the main forces for community life and work. Handicrafts

are always practised in the community to ensure the best yields and guarantee the sustainability of processes and methods. Popular initiatives exist in all areas of activity to strengthen social cohesion and women play a crucial role in these initiatives, in which they account for almost 48% of the active population in Senegal. In a communication, FALL Adou on the basis of ILO data stated that SSE enterprises contribute 40% of GDP and 90% of the creation of new jobs in West African economies. Most urban centres have around 2000000 SSE enterprises, which is enough to boost employment levels in the different cities. The reality is the same in Côte d'Ivoire, mutual aid work, support and associations are traditionally investigated in popular habits. The professionalization of SSE structures is in its infancy with many small structures working alone with all the difficulties that this entails.

3.2 Volunteer motivations in the literature

In the economic literature, volunteer work has been and continues to be the subject of several research studies. Developing a microeconomic perspective, the motivations of volunteers have been analysed. The goal is to identify the motivations for volunteer behaviour and its sensitivity to certain socio-economic variables such as income, cost of time, and family composition (Prouteau, L., & Wolff, F. (2004b). Similarly, the decision to volunteer has been the subject of economic modelling (Mennchik and Weisbrod, 1987; Govekar and Govekar, 2002; Prouteau and Wolf, 2004b). Three of these can be distinguished: the collective goods-production model, the influence model, and the career motivation model.

The collective good production model or production motivation is the model in which individuals volunteer for a so-called "private" reason (Govekar and Govekar, 2002). For the volunteer, this motivation is the search for some kind of reward (Prouteau and Wolf, 2004a, 2004b), such as prestige. It may also consist in seeking a "warm glow", i.e. a pleasant sensation felt by the volunteer after his or her act (Adreoni, 1990). In addition to these different "private" motivations, there is also so-called "pure" altruism (Govekar and Govekar, 2002).

As for the influence and search model or utility motivation, it focuses on the perceived usefulness of the act, the fact of committing oneself to a worthwhile cause (Govekar and Govekar, 2002). Volunteering is most frequently driven by the desire to help others. Most volunteers talk about it with such ease. Some volunteers get involved just to fight for a better life in their community. For example, associations fighting for the rights of vulnerable people (prisoners, children, the poor, the unemployed...).

In the Investment Model or Career Motivation, the volunteer seeks to derive future benefits from his or her act or experience for his or her profession or career, such as new skills and qualifications or encounters that can expand his or her social network (Mennchik and Weisbrod, 1987; Prouteau and Wolf, 2004a, 2004b).

All of these economic models help to structure the motivations for volunteering. The advantage of these models is that they identify broad motivations that differ because of their altruistic, selfish or ambivalent nature (Table 1).

Table 1: Summary of volunteer motivations according to Gournelen (2013)

Great Motivations	Sub-categories (economic model)	Variations
Altruistic motivations	Production of public goods	Producing for others: pure altruism
		Producing services that will benefit a loved one
	Perceived usefulness	Doing something useful
		Getting involved in a worthwhile cause
Hybrid motivations	Production of public goods	Producing and benefiting from services
Selfish motives	Consumption of private goods (immediate incentives) Investment (longterm incentives)	Warm glow (pleasure, pleasant sensation)
		Seeking gratification, prestige, power
		To benefit from the skills and knowledge to be mobilized in a future professional context.

4. Analysis methodology

4.1. Study's data.

Like most of the literature, we surveyed the volunteer population to take into account changes in volunteer involvement behaviours. Our questionnaire consisted of 30 questions, and we targeted those 14 years of age and older who conduct their activities through a duly constituted (formal volunteer) organization. The questionnaire was developed in two formats (paper and online via google Forms) to reach the maximum number of volunteers. The questionnaire is based on literature and has six themes summarized in the table below.

Table 2: Different themes of the questionnaire

Themes	Subject matter
1: Q1 and Q2	Define volunteering; what is it for?
2: Q3 to Q9	My socio-demographic profile. This is for the volunteer to provide personal information about age, gender, marital status, religion, education level etc.
3: Q10 to Q14	My family, emotional and volunteer situation. It aims to establish the link between the practice of volunteering by those close to the volunteer and the decision to volunteer.
4: Q15 to Q21	My volunteer membership. Using a Richter scale, the aim was to provide information on the number of organisations in which he works, the frequency of his participation, the total number of hours etc.
5: Q22 to Q27	My field of work. Here we ask to know a little more about the respondent's volunteer activity
6: Q28 to Q30	My motivations for volunteering. A scale of 4 motivations with 4 questions each is proposed.

The background of the questionnaire in the literature is proposed here.

Table 3: Components of the questionnaire

Concepts	Authors	Questions
Define volunteering; what is it for?	Imagine Canada, 2007	Q1 and Q2
Have a relative or friend volunteer	Personal addition	Q10 and Q11
Having experienced a situation that prompted a volunteer act	Personal addition	Q12 to Q14
Volunteer Membership	Gourmelen, 2014	Q15 to Q21
For altruistic and/or selfish gain.	Bussell and Forbes, 2002	Q28
EMAB	Vallerand and Till, 2000	Q29
Satisfaction of the three innate psychological needs	Forest, J et al, 2010	Q30

This study also mobilizes the 2013 employment survey carried out at the national level by employment policy management agency (AGEPE) with the technical support of the national statistic institute (INS). This database has been reprocessed to take into account the objectives of the study. More than 4,8679 individuals were questioned in the employment survey. After reprocessing this database, 30500 individuals (62.65%), of whom 64 (0.33%) declared volunteering as their main job, make up the sample on which we are working.

In the database resulting from this survey, individuals can be classified according to their status in their main job, which is the variable explained. Thus, self-employed farmers combined with family helpers dominate with 8382 persons for 43.26%. 3555 persons (i.e. 18.35%) are salaried employees, 6427 persons accounting for 33.17% are employers or workers in a field other than agriculture. Only 64 people (or 0.33%) reported volunteering as their main activity. This is easily understandable taking into account the conditions of the survey and also whether volunteering is an unpaid or low paid activity. Volunteers are generally together in the structures that engage them may have been unintentionally omitted. See Table 4 below.

Table 4: Employment status by gender

Employment status	Sex					
	Man		Woman		Total	
	Staff	%	Staff	%	Total number of employees	% Total employment
	Employee	2698	75,89%	857	24,11%	3555
Non-agricultural employer or worker	2569	39,97%	3858	60,03%	6427	31,17%

Voluntary Worker (a)	40	62,5%	24	37,5%	64	0,33%
Trainee or apprentice (b)	647	68,39%	299	31,61%	946	4,89%
ESS (a+b)	687	68,02%	323	31,98%	1010	5,22%
Family assistance or selfemployed farming	4384	52,30%	3998	47,70%	8382	43,26%
Total	10338	53,36%	9036	46,64%	19374	100%

Source: from the author based on ENSETE data, 2013

4.2 Analysis model

Most of our variables are qualitative and polytonic (i.e. having more than 2 modalities). A simple doublecensored Tobit model is used for statistical and econometric estimation. Indeed, the dependent variable which is here the status in employment is a multinomial variable and we want to consider only one or a few modalities of this variable. Tobit models generally refer to regression models in which the domain of definition of the dependent variable is constrained in some form Jacquot, A (2000). Such models were initiated by James Tobin (1958) and mobilized when observations of the explanatory variables and the dependent variable outside a certain range are completely lost Hurlin, C (2003). In general, a simple multi-censored Tobit model is written as follows:

$$y_i = \begin{cases} c_{i,1} & \text{si } y_i^* \leq c_{i,1} \\ y_i^* & \text{si } c_{i,1} < y_i^* \leq c_{i,2} \\ c_{i,2} & \text{si } y_i^* \geq c_{i,2} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Where y_i is the explained variable - status in employment- and y_i^* refers to volunteer involvement. $(c_{i,1}, c_{i,2}) \in \mathbb{R}^2$ designates the censor terminals and where :

$$y_i^* = x_i \beta + \varepsilon_i \quad \forall i = 1, \dots, N \quad (2)$$

Where $x_i = x_i^1 \dots x_i^K$, $\forall i = 1, \dots, N$ designates a vector of observable features and where $\beta = (\beta_1 \dots \beta_K) \in \mathbb{R}^K$ is a vector of unknown parameters and where the disturbances ε_i are distributed according to a distribution law $N(0, \sigma^2_\varepsilon)$.

Let us consider an individual i from a population N ($i = 1, \dots, N$) categorized in $m+1$ modality, who must answer the question: What is the type of the production unit of your main job? His answer must contain within a series of $m+1$ modalities. It is postulated that rational choices can be represented by a utility function $U(\cdot)$. If for each modality $j = 0, 1, \dots, m$, the individual's utility is expressed as :

$$U_j = U(x_j, \varepsilon_j) = v(x_j) + \varepsilon_j \quad \forall j = 0, 1, \dots, m \quad (3)$$

Where $v(\cdot)$ is a deterministic continuous function, x_j , the list of explanatory variables and where ε_j is an i.i.d. random variable whose law is described by the density function $f(\cdot)$ and the distribution function $F(\cdot)$. It is assumed that the perturbations $\varepsilon_j, \forall j = 0, 1, \dots, m$ are independent.

The model used here, the single Tobit with double censorship (friction or Rosett model) is a model where the left and right censorship thresholds are the same for all individuals with $(c_{i,1}, c_{i,2}) \in \mathbb{R}^2$.

$$c_{i,1} = c_1, c_{i,2} = c_2 \quad \forall i = 1, \dots, N \quad (4)$$

$$y_i = \begin{cases} c_1 & \text{si } y_i^* \leq c_1 \\ y_i^* & \text{si } c_1 < y_i^* \leq c_2 \\ c_2 & \text{si } y_i^* \geq c_2 \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

The concentrated log-likelihood associated with a sample $y = (y_1, \dots, y_N)$ in a simple double-censored Tobit model is written as :

$$\log L(y, \beta, \sigma_\varepsilon^2, c_1, c_2) = \sum_{i: y_i = c_1} \log \left[\Phi \left(\frac{c_1 - x_i \beta}{\sigma_\varepsilon} \right) \right] + \quad (6)$$

$$\sum_{i: y_i = c_2} \log \left[1 - \Phi \left(\frac{c_2 - x_i \beta}{\sigma_\varepsilon} \right) \right] - \frac{N}{2} \log(\sigma_\varepsilon^2) - \frac{1}{2\sigma_\varepsilon^2} \sum_{y_i = y_i^*} (y_i - x_i \beta)^2$$

Where N_1 is the number of observations for which $y_i = y_i^*$.

4.3. Analysis of model validity

The accepted Tobit model is justified by the fact that only modality 3= volunteer work of the dependent variable (status in employment) matters here. It is therefore a matter of censoring one on the left and one on the right. The Likelihood function of such a model is written :

$$L(y, \beta, \sigma_\varepsilon^2, c_1, c_2) = \prod_{i: y_i = c_1} \left[\Phi \left(\frac{c_1 - x_i \beta}{\sigma_\varepsilon} \right) \right] \prod_{i: y_i = c_2} \left[1 - \Phi \left(\frac{c_2 - x_i \beta}{\sigma_\varepsilon} \right) \right] \prod_{y_i = y_i^*} \frac{1}{\sigma_\varepsilon} \phi \left(\frac{y_i - x_i \beta}{\sigma_\varepsilon} \right) \quad (7)$$

The first term refers to the product of the probabilities that the observations y_i take the lower censor values c_1 :

$$Prob(y_i = c_1) = Prob(y_i^* \leq c_1) = \Phi \left(\frac{c_1 - x_i \beta}{\sigma_\varepsilon} \right) \quad (8)$$

The second term refers to the product of the probabilities that the observations y_i take the higher censor values c_2 :

$$Prob(y_i = c_2) = Prob(y_i^* \geq c_2) = \Phi \left(\frac{c_2 - x_i \beta}{\sigma_\varepsilon} \right) \quad (9)$$

To measure the goodness of fit of the estimated models, several conventional indicators are considered. There is the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) [Akaike, 1974], the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) [Schwarz, 1978] and P-value ($Prob > \chi^2$) usually used in McFadden's logit and pseudo R^2 models (McFadden, 1974) :

$$AIC = -2LL_M + 2p$$

$$BIC = -2LL_M + \log(n) \times p$$

$$\text{McFadden } R^2 = 1 - \frac{LL_M}{LL_0}$$

With LL_M the log-likelihood, p the number of model parameters to be estimated, n the sample size and LL_0 the log-likelihood of the null model (with no other parameter than the constant or default model). It is formulated as follows:

$$LL_0 = \sum_{j=1}^m n_j \ln \frac{n_j}{n}$$

Where n_j and n denote the number of staff in modality j and the total number of staff in the sample, respectively. The AIC and BIC allow models to be penalized according to the number of parameters in order to satisfy the parsimony criterion, the penalty being even greater with the BIC. The weaker these criteria, the better the model. McFadden R^2 , or pseudo- R^2 , was constructed to resemble the R^2 of linear regression but should be interpreted in terms of the share of deviance and not in terms of the share of variance. Although between 0 and 1 (like R^2), simulations have shown that a value around 0.3 corresponds to a high value of R^2 (Domencich and McFadden [1975, pp. 134-135]).

Another indicator in the econometric literature to judge the quality of the Tobit estimate is the likelihood ratio test formulated as follows : $LR = D_0 - D_M$

With $D_0 = -2LL_0$ deviation from the default template and $D_M = -2LL_M$ deviation from the study design.

The indicator for the likelihood ratio test follows a Chi-square law defined by :

$$LR \sim \chi^2 [(K - 1) * N]$$

With $[(K-1)*N]$ the degree of freedom where K is the number of parameters to be estimated and N is the number of modalities of the dependent variable. The model is of good quality if the calculated value is higher than the value given by the Chi-square table at a fixed threshold α .

The Maximum Likelihood (MV) estimator requires the testing of two main assumptions for the estimation of the Tobit models. These are the heteroskedasticity and normality assumptions.

In general, the estimator of MV in the presence of heteroskedasticity is shown to be asymptotically biased. The importance of the asymptotic biases increases with the degree of censoring of the data.

Greene (1997) proposes the use of a Lagrange multiplier test. An expression of the LM statistic of the null hypothesis test of homoscedasticity $H_0: \alpha = 0$ is

$$LM = N R^2 \text{ which follows a distribution } \chi^2_k$$

Where N denotes the number of observations and R^2 is the coefficient for determining the unit vector regression $e_N = (1, \dots, 1)'$ of dimension $(N, 1)$ on the $K+P + 1$ column of the matrix $G(\hat{\beta}, \hat{\sigma}^2_\varepsilon, 0)$.

$$LM = 0.2183 * 9037 = 1972.7771,$$

This value is much higher than the tabulated value. $\chi^2_{10;0,05} = 18,31$ so the H_0 hypothesis is accepted, there is homoscedasticity.

The second main assumption that can significantly affect the properties of the VM estimator is the assumption of non-normality of disturbances. We use a Schapiro-Wilk test whose formula is :

$$w = \frac{\left[\sum_{i=1}^{\frac{n}{2}} \alpha_i (x_{(n-i+1)} - x_i) \right]^2}{\sum_i (x_i - \bar{x})^2}$$

The W statistic can therefore be interpreted as the coefficient of determination (the square of the correlation coefficient) between the series of quantiles generated from the normal distribution and the empirical quantiles obtained from the data. The higher the W statistic, the more credible the compatibility with the normal distribution. The resulting w is : $0,92 \leq w \leq 1$ for each of the variables. We conclude on the null hypothesis of disturbance normality.

The more complex but more appropriate Hausman test strategy (1978): Nelson (1981), Melenberg and Van Soest (1996) leads to the same conclusion. Estimation work with Maximum Likelihood can be carried out with complete peace of mind.

4.4. Model variables

The database of the employment survey (2013) provides us with several possible variables. But having the objective of analyzing volunteer work in Côte d'Ivoire, we retain only ten variables that are more interesting for us.

- **Status in main job (endogenous variables)**

This variable, as the name implies, determines the status of the individual in his or her main job. It originally consisted of seven modalities, which we reduced to five after treatment:

$$EMPLOYMENT \begin{cases} = 1, \text{if employee} \\ = 2, \text{if employer, non - agricultural worker} \\ = 3, \text{if volunteer worker} \\ = 4, \text{if trainee, apprentice} \\ = 5, \text{if family helper, self - employed farmer} \end{cases}$$

The rational individual chooses his or her job according to his or her own criteria. The explanatory variables should help to understand why individual i chooses modality j , which in our case is fixed to voluntary work.

- **Explanatory variables**

The variables considered relevant to explain the choice of individual i are :

Gender (GENDER): This is the variable that records the influence of gender on the choice to volunteer. It is a dichotomous variable: 1=male and 2=female.

Age (AGE): In 1985, Yavas and Riecken show that age is the most discriminating factor, followed by education and occupation. According to them, a typical volunteer in 1985 was 35 years or older, had reached college, was employed, and had little influence, in terms of time, on his or her family or work.

$$AGE = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if 14 to 24 years old} \\ 2, & \text{if 25 to 34 years old} \\ 3, & \text{if 35 to 44 years old} \\ 4, & \text{if 45 to 54 years old} \\ 5, & \text{if 55 years and older} \end{cases}$$

Relationship to the head of household (**HOUSEHOLDL**): Riecken and Yavas, in collaboration with Wymer (1996), concluded that one of the most influential factors influencing volunteering is parental attitudes about volunteering, which predispose children to participate in this type of activity when they become adults. Friends are also a great source of influence, as is the community when it is small. This variable was categorized into 5 modalities:

$$HOUSEHOLDL = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if head of household} \\ 2, & \text{if spouse of the chief} \\ 3, & \text{if child of the chief} \\ 4, & \text{if relative of the chief} \\ 5, & \text{if other person} \end{cases}$$

Marital status (**MARITALS**): This variable tells us about the relationship between the family status of the individual (volunteer) and his or her involvement in volunteer work :

$$MARITALS = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if married monogamous} \\ 2, & \text{if married polygamous} \\ 3, & \text{if single} \\ 4, & \text{if divorced} \\ 5, & \text{if widowed} \end{cases}$$

Religion (**RELIGION**): This variable, according to our survey, is decisive to the point of being very important according to the respondents. Being a member of a religious community would encourage volunteering (Van Tienen et al., 2010). Some authors find a strong positive correlation between collective religiosity alone and the likelihood of being involved in volunteering in religious (Yeung, 2004) as well as secular organizations (Taniguchi and Thomas, 2011).

$$RELIGION \begin{cases} = 1, & \text{if muslim} \\ = 2, & \text{if catholic} \\ = 3, & \text{if protestant, evangelical} \\ = 4, & \text{if overs religions} \\ = 5, & \text{if animist or no religion} \end{cases}$$

Diploma level (**DIPLOM**): Our survey also revealed a high diploma level of volunteers. Educational attainment is considered one of the most important determinants of volunteering (Chambre, 1984; Wilson,

2000; Handy & Hustinx, 2009). Thus, the higher an individual's level of education, the more likely they are to volunteer (Caro and Bass, 1997, among those aged 55 and older; Choi, 2003).

$$DIPLOM \begin{cases} = 1, \text{if none or CEPE} \\ = 2, \text{if BEPEC, CAP, BEP} \\ = 3, \text{if BAC, BP or BT} \\ = 4, \text{if BAC + 2 or Licence} \\ = 5, \text{if BAC + 4 or higher} \end{cases}$$

Type of production unit (**UPROD**): This variable also reflects the type of employer that might encourage volunteer involvement, especially since volunteer work is also carried out in companies. It includes five modalities which are :

$$UPROD \begin{cases} = 1, \text{if administration, public enterprise} \\ = 2, \text{if private company} \\ = 3, \text{if farm, household} \\ = 4, \text{if international organization} \\ = 5, \text{if associative enterprise (association, cooperative)} \end{cases}$$

Type of employment (**TEMPLOYMENT**): this variable has two modalities

$$TEMPLOY \begin{cases} = 1, \text{if permanent employment} \\ = 2, \text{if casual employment} \end{cases}$$

Place of residence at age 15 (**LRESID**): This variable tells us about the family relationship of the person with whom the individual lived at age 15 and its possible influence on the individual's present decision to volunteer.

$$PRESID \begin{cases} = 1, \text{if at parent's home (father and or mother)} \\ = 2, \text{if at home} \\ = 3, \text{if to the orphélinat} \\ = 4, \text{if at other (guardian)} \end{cases}$$

Is this person (certainly the parent) working (**WORK**) ?

$$PWORK \begin{cases} = 1, \text{if the person is working} \\ = 2, \text{if no} \end{cases}$$

The model to be estimated is like this:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{VOLUNTEER} = & \alpha + \beta \mathbf{SEXE} + \gamma \mathbf{AGE} + \delta \mathbf{HOUSEHOLDL} + \varepsilon \mathbf{MARITALS} + \vartheta \mathbf{RELIGION} \\ & + \mu \mathbf{DIPLOM} + \rho \mathbf{UPROD} + \sigma \mathbf{TEMPLOY} + \varphi \mathbf{PRESID} + \omega \mathbf{PWORK} \end{aligned}$$

The questionnaire envisaged a breakdown into many age groups. A total of seventeen age groups, ranging from 0 to 80 years of age and over and spaced five years apart, were selected. However, for the purposes

of this study, five age groups from 14 to 55 years and over were selected, with a 10-year spacing, with the exception of the last group, which is slightly wider. This choice is not fortuitous, since it was more interesting to include the entire working-age population (individuals aged 14 and over), including retirees. Moreover, it has been shown that retirees are very active in volunteer work due to their greater availability and time pressure (Gourmelen, 2013). Marital status has not received special treatment. As for religion, which is a polytonic variable, it has undergone a reorganization of modalities in order to facilitate analysis and interpretation. Thus, Protestants and other Christians have been grouped together in the same modality (coded M9=3), as have animists and those without religion (coded M9=5).

There were 19 modalities in the variable indicating the level of degree, and they were grouped into 5 modalities. Vocational training diplomas have their equivalents in general education. They can of course be put together for a job like this one. Thus the BAC, BP and BT correspond to the diplomas of the same cycle (second cycle). As well as the DEUG, the Licence, the BTS and the DUT as diplomas of the first cycle of higher education. The Master, the DESS, the DEA, the Ingénieur and the Doctorat, are the diplomas of the second and third university cycle. Other variables such as employment status, type of production unit, etc. were also grouped under five modalities to simplify the analyses. Note that all variables except gender are polytonic variables.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the results of the statistical analysis of the data after processing. Which processing provided a flexible basis more suited to the demands of this work. It is essentially a description of the volunteers studied here.

5.1 Volunteer Motivations

Difficulties encountered in the survey we conducted and the sample size for this work limit the validity of the results to a test of understanding of volunteers and their motivations. Ninety-nine out of 102 individuals confirmed that they had done volunteer work in an organization.

Ivorian volunteers (surveyed) are predominantly male (55.56%), most of them are between 16 and 34 years old with a large proportion (43.43%) under 35 years old and the median age is 24. They are overwhelmingly single (73.74%), religious (86.87% are Christian and 11.11% are Muslim) and have university degrees (47.47% have a Bac+1, +2 or +3 years of study and 36.36% have a Bac+4 or higher). However, only 35.35% are working, 44.44% are still studying and 18.18% are looking for their first job. This points to the great youthfulness of the volunteer population who find in volunteering a way to fight unemployment.

As for their motivations for this work, they are of various kinds. 53.53% volunteer because they have a relative (friend or relative) who does or has done the same work, and also because they have witnessed situations that motivate them to volunteer (82.83%). See box below.

They are also drawn by the difficulties they have experienced themselves (42.42%) and do not want to let anyone else experience such situations. Thus, they get involved through volunteer organizations (18.18% are in at least two organizations), work very often (30.30% at least once a week) and provide at least 2 hours of work each time (35.35%) or more than 3 hours (30.30%) per session.

Box: Volunteer motivation based on life experiences

"A nursery was in a state of insalubrity and I helped clean it up" Mr. Gautier, 28 years old
 "I have seen women in my environment who are not feeding their children well and not taking care of them. So I used my knowledge of nutrition to help her mothers do the Essential Good Practices (EGPs)." Ms. Marlice, 34 years old
 "Individualism, accessibility to education. I taught the abandoned children of a precarious kôkô neighbourhood in Bouaké". Mr. Kennedy Dollar, 27 years old
 "Just this morning I found my old door neighbour collecting bricks, so I couldn't just ignore him and walk by. Mr. Yao, 21 years
 "After graduating from high school, I spent my free time helping students. I did it because I too was a student and I know their difficulties. I didn't have the chance to have tutors " Mr. Kan Constant 26 years old.
 ...

Their characteristic motivations are mixed (39.39%) but revolve around selfish non-self-determined motivation¹ (MNAE 18.18%) for seeking a qualification or professional experience for example. In addition to the question : Why do you volunteer? They answer:

Because the experience I gain from volunteering can eventually be used for employment purposes.	12	30 %
Because volunteering allows me to enrich my resume.	19	47.5 %
Because it allows me to be better considered socially...	14	35 %

5.2 Job characteristics

Who are the volunteers?

By making a descriptive statistic comparing volunteers and non-volunteers, we have :

¹ MNAE is a non-autonomous and therefore extrinsic motivation guided by the search for qualification which is a personal satisfaction.

Table 5: Descriptive statistics between volunteers and non-volunteers

Variables	Volunteers			Non-Volunteers	
	Modalities	Frequenc y	Percentage	Frequenc y	Percentage
Sex	Male	40	62,05%	10298	53,33%
	Female	24	37,95%	9012	46,67%
Age and range	14-24	9	14,06%	4558	23,71%
	25-34	16	25%	5958	30,99%
	35-44	20	31,25%	4103	21,34%
	45-54	8	12,5%	2591	13,48%
	55 and over	11	17,19%	2023	10,52%
Relationship to head of household	Chief	38	59,38%	9645	49,92%
	Chief's spouse	10	15,62%	4813	24,92%
	Child of the chief	10	15,62%	2404	12,45%
	Parent of the chief	6	9,38%	2069	10,71%
	Other	0	0	379	1,96%
Statut matrimonial	Married monogamous	32	50%	10062	52,11%
	Married polygamous	6	9,37%	1860	9,63%
	Single	22	34,38%	6273	32,49%
	Divorced	0	0	281	1,45%
	Widower	4	6,25%	834	4,32%
Religion	Muslim	29	45,31%	10035	51,80%
	Catholic	14	21,87%	3315	17,11%
	Protestant and over	18	28,12%	3085	15,92%
	Other	1	1,56%	328	1,69%
	Animists	2	3,12%	2547	13,15%
Diploma	≤ CEPE	24	54,55%	6935	73,95%
	BEPC et equivalent	7	15,91%	975	10,40%
	BAC et equivalent	6	13,64%	665	7,09%
	<BAC +4	2	4,54%	287	3,06%
	BAC+4 et above	5	11,36%	516	5,50%
Job type	Permanent	52	81,25%	173484	90,24%
	Ocasional	12	18,75%	1826	9,76%

Source: from the author based on ENSETE, 2013

The analysis of this table allows us to say that :

Volunteering is much more practiced by men 62.05% of the survey population. However, the participation rate of women is not to be neglected. The age groups most concerned are the 25 to 44 year olds, with a higher net participation of the 35 to 44 year olds, who account for 31.25% of the population. These volunteers are mostly heads of households (59.38%) and are married to a single woman (50%). The lower participation rate (34.38%) of single persons shows that some of the heads of households are not married. The table also reveals that the practice of volunteering is almost entirely the work of religious people. Christians of all faiths (Catholic, Protestant and others) are more likely to volunteer (49.99%) than Muslims (45.31%). More than one out of two volunteers (54.55%) did not go to college. On the other hand, slightly more of the $\frac{3}{4}$ (52 out of 64) are in permanent employment.

Among non-volunteers, the results are almost the same except for the 25-34 age group (31.41%) and the more numerous Muslims (51.86%) who reverse the trend. Nevertheless, we can conclude that the participation of volunteers and non-volunteers in employment is the same. What motivates some people to volunteer is certainly an internal characteristic -motivation- specific to each one, as noted in the literature (Vallerand and Till, 2000). Certainly, an altruistic or selfish motivation is in the heart, time and circumstances will give him the opportunity to express it. A leader of a group of volunteers suggested these words to us: "Altruism is a gift from God, time and circumstances of life will discover us, and one day or another we will be called a volunteer". Mrs Berté OULAÏ

The volunteers in the database have their main activity in volunteering and make a living from it. This should be understood to mean that this activity is remunerated, but at a low level.

Table 6: Types of volunteers in the database

Type of volunteer work	Staff	Percentage
Religious leader	14	21,88
Volunteer teacher	12	18,75
Trainee, apprentice, manager	25	39,06
Founder	3	4,69
Aid & farmer	10	15,62
Total	64	100

5.3 Analysis of estimation results

The results of the estimation of the simple Tobit model with left- and right-hand censoring are summarised in the table below

Table 7: Tobit Regression Results

Variables	Coefficients	Marginal effects
GENDER	-28.51422***	-28.51422***
AGE	-17.0459***	-17.0459***
MARITALS	2.067341	2.067341
RELIGION	11.03442***	11.03442***
DIPLOM	-21.96551***	-21.96551***
UPROD	114.2761***	114.2761***
TEMPLOYMENT	-28.31921***	-28.31921***
HOUSEHOLDL	16.78534***	16.78534***
LRESID	-1.375246	-1.375246
PWORK	-34.93175***	-34.93175 ***
Constant	-186.9519***	

Significance	Number of observations = 9037
5%	LR chi2(10) = 2747.42
	Prob > chi2 = 0 . 0000
Wald chi2(10) = 3121.85	Pseudo R2 = 0.2183
	Log likelihood = -4918.5998
	AIC = 9861.2
	BIC = 9946,509

Table 7 shows that most of the variables are significant. The $\text{Prob} > \chi^2 = 0.0000 < 5\%$, which means that the model is good overall. The Pseudo R^2 confirms this analysis, as having a low value (0.2183 which also corresponds to a high value of the linear regression R^2), shows the low share of deviance of the variables. This also means that the explanatory variables provide important information for the explanation of the voluntary engagement. The value of LR $\chi^2(10) = 2747.42$ is much higher than its tabulated value. $\chi^2_{0,05}(10) = 18,31$. The AIC and BIC, which allow models to be penalised in order to meet the parsimony criterion, have average values. All these indicators combine to say that the model is well-specified and thus allow for the interpretation of the variables. Marginal effects reflect the effect of a variation in the explanatory variables on the probability of volunteering.

Marginal effects in a censored regression model correspond to the distortion of forecasts on a continuous variable caused by a one-unit change in one of the explanatory variables. In the case of the Tobit model, there are several possible predictions depending on whether one is interested in the censored variable y_i or the latent variable y_i^* . Indeed, three cases can appear Hurlin, C (2003). We consider only the prediction on the censored dependent variable represented by the conditional expectation $\forall i = 1, \dots, N$:

$$E(y_i/x_i, y_i > 0) = E(y_i^*/x_i, y_i^* > 0) = x_i\beta + \sigma_\varepsilon \delta \left(\frac{x_i\beta}{\sigma_\varepsilon} \right)$$

Thus, a variation of 1% in the kth explanatory variable x_i^k for the ith individual, modifies the prediction of the dependent variable y_i for the same individual of ε_{y_i/x_i^k} per cent. We can then calculate an average elasticity $\bar{\varepsilon}_{y_i/x_i^k}$ on all N individuals such as :

$$\bar{\varepsilon}_{y_i/x_i^k} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \varepsilon_{y_i/x_i^k} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{x_i^k \beta^k}{x_i\beta + \sigma_\varepsilon \delta \left(\frac{x_i\beta}{\sigma_\varepsilon} \right)} \right)$$

The model estimates and marginal effects in Table 3 suggest that :

- The variable religion has the greatest effect. It is therefore concluded that the socio-demographic variables have a very strong but negative relationship (except for religion which has a positive relationship and marital status which has none at all) on engagement in volunteer work.
- Socio-professional variables have a great influence on the decision to do volunteer work. While the production unit (35.94% private employment and 45.31% associative employment) that employs the volunteer promotes the choice to volunteer, the type of employment (81.25% permanent employment) discourages it.
- The relationship with the head of the household (59.37% are heads of households themselves) is in a positive and significant relationship, with the variable "Does the parent work?". (90% yes) is significantly and negatively related, and the variable "place of residence at age 15" (74.60% lived with the parents) is not related to the choice of volunteer work. We conclude that the relationship with parents has a significant influence on volunteer involvement.

5.4 Discussion

The main objective of this work is to find out what motivates some people to volunteer. In a context where the labour market is tight and the unemployment rate is high, what guides the choice of certain people called volunteers ? In this quest, the analysis of the characteristics of employed persons, both volunteers and non-volunteers, was carried out first. Next, the case of volunteers was treated specifically. The aim was to consider the relationship between their socio-demographic characteristics and their involvement in volunteering. To analyze the influence of their socio-professional environment on their volunteer involvement. Finally, the relationships between them and their parents since the age of 15 interested us to identify their possible influences.

In the analysis of the first research objective, determining the influence of socio-demographic characteristics on volunteer involvement, the underlying hypothesis was validated that socio-demographic characteristics have a strong influence on volunteer involvement. Age, gender and education have a negative influence, marital status is unrelated, only religion has a strong positive relationship with volunteer

involvement. Individuals who are committed to providing work for others without pay are guided by motivation to volunteer, which is their main characteristic. This motivation is of the type of production of collective goods in the service of the community (Prouteau and Wolf, 204a).

This result, which is somewhat contrary to what the literature says, is due to the small number of volunteers on the base. The level of educational attainment is conducive to volunteer involvement. The literature has noted that the higher an individual's level of education, the more likely they are to volunteer (Caro and Bass, 1997). Indeed, some of the motivations of volunteers are to seek qualifications, training, enrich one's resume, etc., which are in the area of graduate needs.

The relationship between the socio-professional environment and involvement in volunteering is well established. This relationship is positive with the employer, mainly private, but negative with the type of job. In the literature, volunteer involvement is driven by motivation. The more the individual knows the type of job that is offered to him, the less he will engage in volunteering.

In terms of relationships with parents and its possible influences on volunteer involvement. Estimation results showed that most of the volunteers in the sample, 59.37% are heads of households, 76.93% lived with parents at age 15 (Prouteau & Wolf, 2004a, 2004b) and 90% of these parents are working. This confirms that the relationship with parents has a considerable influence on volunteer involvement. However, there is a restriction on having lived with parents at age 15 that has nothing to do with volunteer involvement, according to our results. This restriction can be explained by the age group (35 to 44 years) where individuals volunteer the most (31.25%). Until this age group, future volunteers no longer live with their parents, so they are subject to other socio-economic influences that would lead them to opt for wellpaid work instead.

However, the influence of parents' socio-professional situation on volunteer involvement is strong but negative. The more socially stable the parents are, the less the children engage in this type of work. With utility motivation, volunteers enjoy and satisfy themselves by helping others. It is also a way for them to give back what they have received from their parents in terms of the love they pass on to the needy. In fact, they feel a social obligation to those around them, to society (Fitch, 1978). Their "private" motivation would be in addition to or replace so-called "pure" altruism (Govekar and Goverkar, 2002).

5.5 Conditions for successful EHS

Volunteering through the structures of the social and solidarity economy is of great importance in an economy in search of development such as ours. In order to take advantage of this, according to what emerges from this study, a few recommendations are feasible, with respect to politics:

- Creating the conditions for the development of the social and solidarity economy ;
- Encourage the development of associations through monitoring structures ;

- Encourage the professionalization of voluntary structures (associations, mutual societies, cooperatives and foundations) ;
- Promote volunteering in companies through social responsibility entrusted to them followed by tax breaks to encourage them to do so ;
- Encourage them to set up formal volunteer programs in companies and even in the community.

6. CONCLUSION

The main objective of this study was to show the influence of socio-demographic characteristics in the choice of voluntary work.

At the end of the study, two main conclusions emerge. The motivation for volunteering stems from the relationship with parents from an early age. It is love, the gift of self learned from them. Volunteer motivation is guided by socio-demographic characteristics, mainly religion. It is reinforced by the individual's employing structure, whether private or associative.

Children who receive a lot of paternal affection are more likely to give it through volunteering. As for parents or employers (volunteers), as a result of their commitment or sensitivity to this work, their children or employees end up being intrinsically motivated to get involved as well. Through this self-giving, volunteers can initiate the professionalization of their structures (associations, cooperatives, mutual societies and foundations) and constitute an important branch of the social and solidarity economy (SSE).

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